

Quantum Environment Generator

Quantum Environment Generator for Tunneling for Atomic Transmutation and Fusion Reaction or Quantum Tunneling as described at SIU is a quantum environment in which the plasma is kept that leads to a very low force atomic reactions and the output energy is much higher than the initial energy or input energy. The project is classified under Systematic Invention Unit.

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The physical environment system will influence during their development and formation. This stage will provide information regarding their potential **shape** under mechanical stress and physical space constraints within the...

